

STEFANO REALE, CECILIA COSTA, RAFFAELE DALL'OLIO, EUGENIA OLIVERI,
SILVIA SCIBETTA, SUSANNA GIARDINA, TIZIANA LUPO, FEDERICA BRUNO,
GERMANO CASTELLI, ANTONELLA MIGLIAZZO, CARMELO BONGIORNO
& FABRIZIO VITALE

MOLECULAR PROFILES TO ESTIMATE THE GENETIC
VARIABILITY IN THE SICILIAN HONEY BEE POPULATION

*Profili Molecolari per stimare la variabilità genetica
nella popolazione di api siciliane*

The geographical distribution of Mediterranean honey bee subspecies is influenced by various factors: migrations, trade of honey bee queens, intercrossing with other non-autochthonous subspecies which could lead to a loss of diversity according to natural laws. The study of the diversity and genetic structure of Sicilian honey bees is classically based on the morphological analysis of the wings. Recently this has been integrated by a molecular approach, based on the analysis of mitochondrial DNA and on a set of appropriately selected polymorphic nuclear markers to even better characterize the subspecies. In the framework of the project “APESLOW” funded by the Sicilian regional administration, a group of *Apis mellifera* colonies from various parts of Sicily were selected in order to build a database containing the genetic profiles of Sicilian bees. Based on reference samples provided by CREA, a number of samples examined showed different levels of hybridization between *A. m. siciliana* and *A. m. ligustica*. Our approach describes the effectiveness of genetic measures aimed at the conservation of *A. m. siciliana* in restricted geographical areas and at the recovery of the residual genetic variability of *A. m. siciliana*.

The database is used to certify the subspecies from a genetic point of view, to study the allelic frequencies of the subspecies of honey bees, to implement research in the field of bees' adaptation to climate and environmental changes. According to previous molecular studies (GARNERY *et al.*, 1993; FRANCK *et al.*, 2000b), the two most widespread Italian subspecies have

a hybrid origin. Although nuclear markers (microsatellite loci) confirmed the Eastern European inheritance of both subspecies, analysis of mitochondrial DNA (mtDNA) indicated that *A. m. ligustica* represents a composite of European lineages over much of the Italian peninsula, while in Sicily only haplotypes of the African lineage have been found. The original Sicilian *Apis mellifera* population, previously called *A. m. sicula* Montagano, 1911 (= *Apis mellifera siciliana* Dalla Torre, 1896) differs from *A. m. ligustica* and other Mediterranean subspecies from both a behavioural and ecological point of view. According to beekeeper reports, its ability to reduce or stop brood rearing during the summer months, when pollen and nectar sources are scarce, also controls infestations of the *Varroa* parasitic mite, making it the preferred subspecies for honey production in the arid central area of Sicily. Beekeeping in Sicily has very ancient origins, as the island is located on the main trade routes of the Phoenicians, Greeks and Carthaginians. As a result, Sicilian honey bee populations may also have incorporated various genetic traits from African and/or Near Eastern lineages. Stocks of *A. m. ligustica* from northern Italy were introduced in Sicilian apiaries, mainly in the eastern part of the island, and have now spread to the rest of the island, hybridizing with the native *A. m. siciliana* populations. Since 1988, colonies of *A. m. siciliana* have been transferred and reproduced in the smaller Sicilian islands (Ustica, Aeolian Islands: Filicudi and Vulcano).

These colonies were crossed with colonies of *A. m. siciliana* originating from western Sicily, to counteract the effects of inbreeding. The conservation program of the small islands has continued over the years allowing the recovery and conservation of the Sicilian subspecies. About 1500 bee samples were analysed following thermal genomic DNA extraction from the legs of each individual. The DNA samples were then processed for determination of the molecular assets of a complex panel of markers (micro satellites). The loci considered are 12 in two distinct direct reactions on the loci: Ap043, A113, A007, A088, A (B) 124 and Ap055 for panel 1; A079, A008, Ap226, A043, A029 and A014 for panel 2. The amplicons were examined by capillary electrophoresis on sequencer 3500 Applied Biosystems. The genotypic profiles were read and analysed using the GeneMapper ID v4.0 software. STRUCTURE 2.3.4 software was used to infer the genetic structure and admixture level of honey bee colonies by estimating the most likely number of populations (k) determined with 10 replicated runs with 80,000 iterations according to Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC). Only samples above this threshold were considered for the assembly of genetic databases. The ARLEQUIN allelic database v3.5 was employed to estimate the number of alleles (N_a) and frequencies at each locus (A_f), the observed and expected heterozygosity (H_o and H_e). GenAlEx 6.502 software was used to perform principal component

analysis (PCA) and to obtain the mean number of haplotypes (Nh), the number of private haplotypes (pNh) and the diversity of haplotypes (D) and the genetic distance between populations. By applying this experimental and bioinformatic protocol, over the years a database has been implemented which shows a trend of allelic combinations increasingly tending towards the genetic purity of the Sicilian subspecies (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 — The database as shown by the software STRUCTURE. In green the *A. m. ligustica* genotype, in red the *A. m. siciliana* genotype.

Aknowledgements — Funding was provided by the Sicily Region in the framework of the research project 2012-2015 “Reintroduzione e conservazione della sottospecie a rischio estinzione *Apis mellifera siciliana* Dalla Torre, 1896” (APESLOW)”.

REFERENCES

- FRANCK P., GARNERY L., CELEBRANO G., SOLIGNAC M. & CORNUET J.M., 2000. Hybrid origins of honeybees from Italy (*Apis mellifera ligustica*) and Sicily (*A. m. sicula*). *Molecular Ecology*, 9: 907-921.
- GARNERY L., SOLIGNAC M., CELEBRANO G. & CORNUET J.M., 1993. A simple test using restricted PCR-amplified mitochondrial DNA to study the genetic structure of *Apis mellifera* L. *Experientia*, 49: 1016-1021.

Authors' Addresses — S. REALE, E. OLIVERI, S. SCIBETTA, S. GIARDINA, F. BRUNO, G. CASTELLI, A. MIGLIAZZO & F. VITALE, Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale della Sicilia - A. Mirri, Via Gino Marinuzzi, 3 - 90129 Palermo (I); email: stefano.reale@izssicilia.it; oliverieugenia@gmail.com; C. COSTA, Centro di ricerca agricoltura ed ambiente - Consiglio per la Ricerca in Agricoltura e l'Analisi dell'Economia Agraria (CREA-AA), Via di Saliceto, 80 - 40121 Bologna (I); cecilia.costa@crea.gov.it; R. DALL'OLIO, BeeSources, Bologna (I); email: raffaele.dallolio@gmail.com.